
Recent trends and seasonal patterns in U.K. nitrous oxide emissions (2013-2022) *

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Overview

- Top-down (measurement-derived) emissions are 14-33% higher than 2022 inventory-reported values across 2013-2022 for the U.K.
- Top-down emissions suggest a negative emissions trend for the U.K. across 2013-2022 that is not seen in the emissions inventory.
- Synthesis of top-down and bottom-up approaches suggest emissions differences could be attributed to agricultural N₂O sources, but missing or indirect N₂O emissions could also contribute.
- Without an established tracer for distinguishing sources of N₂O emissions, inventories are relied on for the spatial distribution of sources.

*This document is primarily based on results presented in “Combining top-down and bottom-up approaches to evaluate recent trends and seasonal patterns in U.K. N₂O emissions” by Saboya et al., submitted to: *JGR: Atmospheres* ¹².

Background

Nitrous oxide (N₂O) is widely considered the third most important anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) after carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄)^{1,2}. This is due to a combination of its atmospheric abundance of around 330 parts-per-billion (ppb)³, its atmospheric lifetime of over 100 years^{1,4} and its global warming potential of 265 times that of CO₂ over a 100-year time horizon¹. Since the global phase-out of chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and other ozone-depleting substances, N₂O is the largest remaining threat to the stratospheric ozone layer⁵.

Between 1750 and 2018 global atmospheric N₂O concentrations increased by more than 20%. The global rise in atmospheric N₂O concentrations is primarily driven by emissions associated with our need for food^{a 1,2,5}, with human-induced emissions increasing by 30% from the 1980s (5.6 (3.6-8.7) Tg N₂O yr⁻¹) to 2016 (7.3 (4.2-11.4) Tg N₂O yr⁻¹)¹.

Rapid reductions of N₂O emissions could account for 5-10% of the remaining carbon budget for a 2 °C world^{7,8}. Despite the possibility of N₂O emissions reductions significantly contributing to achieving critical climate goals, N₂O has largely been ignored in policy and international climate negotiations².

^a The Haber-Bosch process used to produce synthetic fertilisers is responsible for 1.4% of global CO₂ emissions and uses 1% of global energy consumption⁶. Direct soil emissions from fertiliser applications are the primary agricultural N₂O source, with livestock manure emissions also a significant N₂O source¹. Global agricultural N₂O emissions of 7.3 Tg N₂O yr⁻¹ were estimated for 2007-2016¹.

U.K. inventory reported N₂O emissions

N₂O emissions reported in the U.K. National Inventory Reports state a ~40% decrease of N₂O emissions occurred between 1990 and 2021⁹. The closure of certain U.K. nitric acid and adipic acid production facilities heavily contributed to a decrease in emissions⁷. Since c. 2010, U.K. N₂O emissions have remained relatively constant at 0.75 Tg N₂O yr⁻¹ (Figure 1).

Figure 1: 1990-2021 U.K. N₂O emissions reported in the 2023 National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory/UNFCCC.

U.K. N₂O emissions from atmospheric measurements

Atmospheric GHG measurements have long been used for monitoring changes in the atmosphere's chemical composition. Atmospheric GHG concentration measurements can inform on surface emissions when used with an atmospheric inverse model, such as InTEM¹⁰ or RHIME^{11,12} (**Box 1**).

The U.K. DECC (Deriving Emissions linked to Climate Change) network (Figure 2) established in 2012 currently comprises of five measurement stations that have been continuously measuring atmospheric concentrations of numerous GHGs.

The locations of the measurement stations in the U.K. and Republic of Ireland mean atmospheric trace gas measurements can provide more precise empirical constraints on U.K. GHG emissions than countries with a sparser network or without a measurement network.

Figure 2: U.K. DECC Network.

Box 1: Overview of atmospheric inverse methods

Take a set of atmospheric concentration measurements. These could be of CO₂, CH₄, N₂O or some other trace gas. These data can inform on the changes in atmospheric composition over time (is the atmospheric concentration of a trace gas increasing or decreasing). But alone, these measurements cannot inform on surface emissions and where they occur, which is the information needed to ensure emissions reduction targets are achieved.

For long-lived trace gases, such as N₂O, atmospheric concentrations are directly proportional to surface emissions:

$$\text{concentrations} \propto \text{emissions}$$

Atmospheric transport models relate emissions to atmospheric concentrations using a combination of Gaussian plume modelling, random-walk physics, and meteorological fields.

An atmospheric inverse model uses atmospheric concentration measurements to calculate how much a bottom-up (**prior**) emissions estimate would need to be scaled to minimise the mismatch with the observations. The advantage of the inverse approach is that it also provides spatial information on where higher or lower emissions are likely to have occurred.

U.K. N₂O emissions and trends (2013-2022)

Figure 3 shows that top-down emissions derived using atmospheric measurements from the U.K. DECC network in the InTEM and RHIME models were on average higher than those reported in the 2022 U.K. National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory (NAEI) by **14-33% (17-33 Gg N₂O yr⁻¹)** over 2013-2022. Differences between the InTEM and RHIME emissions estimates can be attributed to differences in how background concentrations are calculated, how model uncertainties are defined, and differences in the inverse approach.

Previous U.K. studies ^{10,14} using fewer measurement stations found top-down (measurement-derived) estimates were 13-22% lower than the inventory estimates reported *at that time*. The entire U.K. NAEI is revised each year to reflect changes in emissions factors, activity data etc.

Top-down InTEM and RHIME emissions indicate negative trends of -0.7 ± 0.5 and -2.1 ± 0.7 Gg N₂O yr⁻², respectively, over 2013-2022. These trends are not statistically significant (Table 1) because of their large uncertainties. This contrasts N₂O inventory (bottom-up) emissions which remain relatively constant over this period.

Figure 3: Annual measurement-derived U.K. N₂O emissions from InTEM inverse model (red) and RHIME inverse model (blue) along with the linear trends for 2013-22 that are extrapolated to 2030, with 2030 values indicated by circular markers. Current U.K. NAEI emissions and U.K. DESNZ projected emissions are shown in black. ¹⁰

Table 1: R² and p-value from weighted linear regressions of 2013-2022 trend.

	p> t	R ²
InTEM	0.20	0.19
RHIME	0.02	0.52

U.K. N₂O seasonal cycles

The U.K. Emissions Model (UKEM) developed by the U.K. Centre for Ecology and Hydrology uses a range of data sources to provide monthly U.K. sub-sector N₂O emissions (Figure 4-5). The UKEM model indicates N₂O emissions are mostly from agricultural applications of synthetic fertilisers which are also responsible for the seasonal emissions peak occurring in the spring (Mar.-May).

There are discrepancies between the 2013-2022 averaged top-down and UKEM seasonal cycles in the magnitude and timing of the main seasonal peak (Figure 4). For certain years, a secondary peak occurring in the late summer is also observed in the top-down emissions.

Figure 4: 2013-2022 averaged monthly U.K. N₂O emissions. ¹⁰

To resolve the top-down and bottom-up seasonal discrepancies, six UKEM emissions sub-sectors with pronounced seasonal patterns (Figure 5) - with all remaining N₂O emissions aggregated into “other” - were optimised to match the RHIME (Figure 5b) and InTEM (Figure 5c) averaged seasonal cycles. The UKEM temporal profiles were unaltered (e.g. synthetic fertiliser emissions must always peak in late spring).

The optimisation indicates a decrease of ~27 Gg N₂O yr⁻¹ in synthetic fertiliser N₂O and an increase of ~5 Gg N₂O yr⁻¹ in manure N₂O emissions reduces the top-down bottom-up mismatch. The optimisations also indicate the largest emissions increases (~34 Gg N₂O yr⁻¹) are from the aggregated sub-sectors that do not exhibit seasonal cycles. There is poor agreement between the optimised UKEM sub-sector emissions and the top-down seasonal cycles for most of the year. This suggests some of the UKEM sub-sector temporal profiles are at odds with the N₂O measurements and modelling.

Figure 5: 2013-2022 average N₂O seasonal emissions profiles. (a) Disaggregated sub-sector emissions profiles as modelled in UKEM. Average RHIME and InTEM top-down seasonal emissions (solid lines) and 68% confidence intervals (dashed lines) with corresponding mean posterior sub-sector emissions are shown in (b) and (c), respectively.

Outlook

- Top-down U.K. N₂O emissions are 14-33% higher than 2022 inventory reported emissions across 2013-2020 and have large uncertainties.
- Top-down U.K. N₂O emissions indicate negative trends over 2013-2022 which are not statistically significant. There is no emissions trend in the inventory. There is no indication in the atmospheric measurements of what could be driving this trend.
- Top-down bottom-up differences could be attributed to underestimated livestock manure sources (which have large uncertainties). But there could also be missing sources or emissions from indirect sources that are unaccounted for in the inventory.
- Without an established tracer of N₂O emissions, we heavily rely on the inventory for the source distribution of N₂O emissions.
- Detailed information about agricultural sources (temporal and spatial patterns) and their uncertainties could improve U.K. N₂O emissions estimates and resolve top-down bottom-up discrepancies.
- Further information about U.K. N₂O emissions can be found in Saboya et al.¹²

References

- ¹ Tian, H., Xu, R., Canadell, J. G., Thompson, R. L., Winiwarter, W., Suntharalingam, P., Davidson, E. A., Ciais, P., Jackson, R. B., Janssens-Maenhout, G., Prather, M. J., Regnier, P., Pan, N., Pan, S., Peters, G. P., Shi, H., Tubiello, F. N., Zaehle, S., Zhou, F., ... Yao, Y. (2020). A comprehensive quantification of global nitrous oxide sources and sinks. *Nature*, 586(7828). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2780-0>
- ² Kanter, D. R., Ogle, S. M., & Winiwarter, W. (2020). Building on Paris: integrating nitrous oxide mitigation into future climate policy. In *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* (Vol. 47). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2020.04.005>
- ³ Lan, X., K.W. Thoning, and E.J. Dlugokencky: Trends in globally averaged CH₄, N₂O, and SF₆ determined from NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory measurements. Version 2024-02, <https://doi.org/10.15138/P8XG-AA10>
- ⁴ Prather MJ, Hsu J, DeLuca NM, Jackman CH, Oman LD, Douglass AR, Fleming EL, Strahan SE, Steenrod SD, Søvde OA, Isaksen IS, Froidevaux L, Funke B. Measuring and modeling the lifetime of nitrous oxide including its variability. *J Geophys Res Atmos*. 2015 Jun 16;120(11):5693-5705. doi: 10.1002/2015JD023267. Epub 2015 Jun 5. PMID: 26900537; PMCID: PMC4744722.
- ⁵ Ravishankara, A. R., Daniel, J. S., & Portmann, R. W. (2009). Nitrous oxide (N₂O): The dominant ozone-depleting substance emitted in the 21st century. *Science*, 326(5949). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1176985>
- ⁶ Capdevila-Cortada, M. (2019). Electrifying the Haber–Bosch. In *Nature Catalysis* (Vol. 2, Issue 12). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41929-019-0414-4>
- ⁷ Kanter, D. R. (2018). Nitrogen pollution: a key building block for addressing climate change. *Climatic Change*, 147(1–2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-017-2126-6>
- ⁸ United Nations Environment Programme (2013) Drawing down N₂O to protect climate and the ozone layer: a UNEP synthesis report. Available at: <https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/8489> (Accessed: 23 February 2024)
- ⁹ Brown, P., Cardenas, L., del Vento, S., Karagianni, E., MacCarthy, J., Mullen, P., Passant, N., Richmond, B., Thistlethwaite, G., Thomson, A., Wakeling, D., & Willis, D. (2023). UK Greenhouse Gas Inventory, 1990 to 2021 Annual Report for Submission under the Framework Convention on Climate Change.
- ¹⁰ Manning, A. J., Redington, A. L., Say, D., O'Doherty, S., Young, D., Simmonds, P. G., Vollmer, M. K., Mühle, J., Arduini, J., Spain, G., Wisher, A., Maione, M., Schuck, T. J., Stanley, K., Reimann, S., Engel, A., Krummel, P. B., Fraser, P. J., Harth, C. M., ... Arnold, T. (2021). Evidence of a recent decline in UK emissions of hydrofluorocarbons determined by the InTEM inverse model and atmospheric measurements. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 21(16), 12739–12755. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-21-12739-2021>
- ¹¹ Ganesan, A. L., Rigby, M., Zammit-Mangion, A., Manning, A. J., Prinn, R. G., Fraser, P. J., Harth, C. M., Kim, K. R., Krummel, P. B., Li, S., Mühle, J., O'Doherty, S. J., Park, S., Salameh, P. K., Steele, L. P., & Weiss, R. F. (2014). Characterization of uncertainties in atmospheric trace gas inversions using hierarchical Bayesian methods. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 14(8). <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-14-3855-2014>
- ¹² Saboya, Eric., Manning, Alistair., Levy, Peter., Stanley, Kieran., Pitt, Joseph., Young, Dickon., Say, Daniel., Grant, Aoife., Arnold, Tim., Rennick, Chris., Tomlinson, Samuel., Carnell, Edward., Artioli, Yuri., Stavert, Ann., Spain, T., O'Doherty, Simon., Rigby, Matt., Ganesan, Anita. (2024). Combining top-down and bottom-up approaches to evaluate recent trends and seasonal patterns in U.K. N₂O emissions. 10.22541/essoar.170689049.90211430/v1.
- ¹³ Ganesan, A. L., Manning, A. J., Grant, A., Young, D., Oram, D. E., Sturges, W. T., Moncrieff, J. B., & O'Doherty, S. (2015). Quantifying methane and nitrous oxide emissions from the UK and Ireland using a national-scale monitoring network. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 15(11), 6393–6406. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-15-6393-2015>
- ¹⁴ Manning, A. J., O'Doherty, S., Jones, A. R., Simmonds, P. G., & Derwent, R. G. (2011). Estimating UK methane and nitrous oxide emissions from 1990 to 2007 using an inversion modeling approach. *Journal of Geophysical Research Atmospheres*, 116(2), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010JD014763>